

ANALYSIS OF SOME ECONOMIC TERMS TRANSLATED FROM GERMAN INTO RUSSIAN

ANÁLISIS DE ALGUNOS TÉRMINOS DE ECONOMÍA TRADUCIDOS DEL ALEMÁN AL RUSO

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RESUMEN

El objetivo de la investigación fue analizar los términos económicos en alemán y ruso. Se describe como una investigación analítica cuyos resultados indicaron que los términos económicos se clasifican en cuatro grupos: no hay equivalente en el idioma de destino, traducido en diccionario, pero necesita definición, se percibe fácilmente pero su traducción es difícil, posee significado, pero para comprender su significado se requiere de una descripción adicional. Este documento muestra que los términos económicos son de alguna manera desconocidos y difíciles de aprender para los estudiantes, por lo que es necesario definirlos sobre la base de las características lingüísticas y culturales de Rusia.

Palabras clave: texto económico, traducción, equivalencia, características lingüísticas y culturales.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to analyze some economic terms in German and Russian. It was an analytical research whose findings indicated that economic terms are classified into four lacunae groups while translating them into Russian: no equivalent in the target language, term found in dictionaries but need extra definition, easily perceived by the reader but its translation is difficult, and, finally, meaning found but unclear understanding of its meaning in discourse as it requires extra description. This paper shows that economic terms are somehow unfamiliar and difficult to learn for students, and it is necessary to define them on the basis of linguistic and cultural features of Russia.

Keywords: economic text, translation, linguistic equivalence, linguistic and cultural features.

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INTRODUCTION

Language as a means of communication and common understanding among the people of a region plays a fundamental role. However, to reach this common understanding between languages has been a problem for a very long time. Due to cultural, social, and economic changes, language has evolved and expanded its vocabulary. Advances and expansions in technology, philosophy, and knowledge have originated innumerable terms, being the field of economy an example. In this case, specialized words and terms have been created, and their translation into another language requires an attempt beyond literal or word-for-word translation. Sorokin and Markovina (1988) accurately selected the term "lacuna".

For them, the term *lacuna* refers to all the phenomena that require further clarification when contacting a different culture. As lacunarity is found in almost all languages of the world, they consider it as an appropriate and methodologically justified term used when comparing not only languages, but also some other aspects of culture. On the one hand, this expansion of the concept of *lacuna* is based on a real close relationship between language and culture; on the other hand, the identification along with linguistic and cultural lacunae can, in their opinion, contribute to the establishment of some specific forms of correlation between language and culture (Sorokin and Markovina, 1988).

It is incorrect to refer only about the absence of an equivalent word in another language, as, sometimes, this lack of equivalence will need a stable phrase combination to represent the term (or idiom) in another language. Therefore, lacunae refers not only to single foreign words or terms, but also to phrases whose combination helps to achieve meaning in another language, that is, to express meaning in the target language, the translator will need to give a verbose explanation of its meaning.

Accurate perception of an international issue may lead to better economic ties between countries. However, there are a lot of barriers in translation of economy texts from the German language into the Russian one. Words and terms cannot be translated into another language without taking into account the linguistic and cultural context of the source language; in other words, translation of one word or term requires the accurate perception of meaning of that specific concept in the source language.

On the other hand, translation into the target language is very difficult because words and expressions must be used in the way that target language speakers perceive them on the basis of linguistic and cultural features of their country. In fact, the problem is that sometimes an equivalent is not found in the target language, and the words of the target language are not potent enough to render the proper meaning of that specific word or term. At this point, a true translation of the word does not occur, or an imperfect and incorrect concept of the word is

formed in the target language. This research is conducted to investigate these differences as problems in translation of some economy terms from German to Russian.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, terms related to economy in German and Russian were studied and analyzed through discourse analysis. To do this, a list of economy terms with a major focus on the term “*market*” was provided in German and Russian. Then, through discourse analysis, meanings of the terms in their cultural and linguistic context were provided. Afterwards, the obtained results were compared, and, in the end, a final analysis was completed based on the proper implication of these terms along with their international concepts.

DISCUSSION

Through the recognition of the fact that what the term implies is more important than the word itself, this research determined the implications of one word in two distinct cultures and languages. Several issues of digest «Markt», namely «Marktlexikon» were used. At this stage we were interested not in the creation of a dictionary or glossary, which includes the body of lacunae of the studied subjects, but to build a sample that represents the diversity. The articles of Marktlexikon reveal exactly the concept of lacunarity, which can be attributed, in these cases, to interlingual and intercultural lacuna, that is, it requires explanations for readers of the digest. The analysis of the vocabulary in these texts allowed us to distinguish four types of lacunae

The first group includes lacunae that do not have a commonly used equivalent in the target language; therefore, it requires a description to explain their meaning. These lexemes often have two options – the full designation and abbreviated name, as are the names of laws, regulations, concepts expressed by complex word-formation constructions. As examples, consider 3 lexemes of complex words, as they appeared in the article used. Translation of these lexemes offered only by online dictionary Multitran.ru (<https://www.multitran.ru>, n.d):

Allgemeinverbindlichkeitserklärung (AVE) - administrative act on labor standards; **Arbeitnehmer-Entsendegesetz(AEntG)** - law on labor standards for foreign workers;

Altersteilzeit - partial retirement.

However, the translation of the term itself does not reflect its content aspect, which can be identified only through the definition or comment given in the text of the article. Therefore, the student-translator faces the task not only to find or give the translation of such lexical units, but also to make the translation of the explanatory

text to fill the existing lacuna. An example of such an explanation is the text on partial retirement:

Altersteilzeitrichtetsich an ältereArbeitnehmer. Beschäftigteab 55 Jahrenhaben die Möglichkeit, ihreArbeitszeitzureduzierenoderihreaktiveTätigkeitvorzeitigzubeenden, um so den Übergang in den Ruhestandvorzubereiten. Die vorzeitigeBeendigung der aktivenTätigkeitwird in Deutschland am häufigstengenutzt. Das sogenannteBlockmodellwird in zweiPhasenunterteilt: die Arbeitsphase und die Freistellungsphase.

Even more interesting, in this sense, is the complex word formed as a result of binding: "**1-Euro-Job**" and representing the periphrasis of the official complex name: "**ArbeitsgelegenheitenmitMehraufwandsentschädigung**" (AGH-MAE). The explanatory text makes it possible to fill the intercultural lacuna:

Die Grundidee der AGH-MAE istes, Arbeitslose, die schonlängereZeitArbeitslosengeldbeziehen, wieder an einenormaleBeschäftigungzugewöhnen und dadurcheinefesteAnstellungzuerreichen. Dem ArbeitgeberentstehenkeinePersonalkosten, der BetroffeneerhältauchkeinenLohn, sondern von der Arbeitsagentureine, Mehraufwandsentschädigung“ alsZuschusszudemArbeitslosengeld.

But it does not help to find a suitable option to fill in the interlingual lacuna. Since both complex lexemes are not represented in the available dictionaries. The student-translator should choose between compensating or filling the lacuna using a descriptive construction.

The second group includes lacunae that have a translation option in the dictionary, but require explanations for their adequate understanding. The lacunae of this group are close to the first. Their main difference is that they are represented in dictionaries. To illustrate this phenomenon, we give both a translation of the lexical units themselves, and texts that explain their meaning.

ArbeitsaufAbruf- labor efforts of the worker depending on the quantity of work.

Bei**ArbeitsaufAbruf**werdendieArbeitsstundenvonderbeschäftigten Person nurabgeleistet, wennbeimArbeitgebertatsächlichArbeitvorliegt. Diese Art von Arbeitsverhältniswirdvertraglichgeregelt. Die vertraglicheRegelung muss den Umfang der täglichenbzw. wöchentlichenArbeitszeitumfassen. Fehlt die AngabeeinerkonkretenArbeitszeit, gilt ein 10-stündiger Umfang pro Wochebzw. ein 3-stündiger Umfang pro Werktag. KommtesmangelsArbeitnichtzurArbeitsleistung des Beschäftigten, so ist der Arbeitgeberdazuverpflichtet, dennoch den Lohnfür die entsprechendeArbeitszeitzuleisten. LiegteineKrankmeldungvor, so erhält der Arbeitnehmer den vollenLohn.

Generationenvertrag, der –intergenerational agreement

Generationenvertrag bezeichnet ein nicht fixiertes, aber praktiziertes „Vertrag“ zwischen der jüngeren, berufstätigen und der älteren, nicht mehr berufstätigen Generation, bei dem jeweils die jüngere Generation für Renten und andere Zahlungen der älteren Generation aufkommt.

Halbtagsarbeit, die - work on a reduced [half] working day; part-time job
=Halbtagsbeschäftigung -work for half a day.

Halbtagsarbeit umfasst die Hälfte der betrieblichen Arbeitszeit bei Vollzeitbeschäftigung. Sie kann entweder vormittags, nachmittags oder an zwei und einem halben Tag pro Woche abgeleistet werden. Halbtagsarbeit ist zur Zeit die häufigste Form von Teilzeitarbeit in Deutschland.

The third group includes lacunae that are easily understood by the recipient, but are difficult to translate since they do not have a commonly used equivalent in Russian. These are words like:

Beitragszahler – payer of contributions (by analogy with taxpayer);

Geringqualifizierte, der – low-skilled worker;

Leistungsempfänger – recipient of services, (social security) recipient of benefits or pension;

Langzeitarbeitslose, der – person receiving long-term unemployment benefits.

Lexical units that require compensation were also included into this group:

Industrienation- an industrial country (not a nation).

The fourth group includes intercultural lacuna whose translations are found in dictionaries, but do not have equivalents in the economy discourse of the recipient. Therefore, for an adequate understanding, they also require explanations, that is, a linguistic-cultural comment. The dictionary already contains such a comment filling the lacuna because the dictionary entry is not a translation of the word, but the explanation of the term. These are lexical units as:

Arbeitszeitregelung, die - regulation of working hours;

Kündigungsschutz, der-protection against unreasonable dismissal of workers and employees (FRG), 2) guarantee against unreasonable eviction from the apartment;

Pflegeversicherung, die - care insurance, long-term care insurance, patient care insurance;

Praxisgebühr, die - quarterly fee of 10 euros, charged at the first quarter of doctor's visit;

Tarifparteie, **Tarifvertragspartei**, die - party to the collective agreement;

Tarifvertragspartner, der - party in a tariff agreement;

Tarifvertrag; der - collective bargaining agreement (FRG), tariff agreement, collective labour agreement (can serve as a basis for individual employment agreements, usually between trade unions and employers' Union);

Tarifvertragsgesetz, das - the law on tariff agreements, the law on the procedure for concluding collective (labor) contracts (FRG).

The analysis of the lacunarity of economic texts showed that there is a relationship between the phenomenon of untranslatability and linguacultural factors. Their content cannot be adequately understood if there is a difference in the cultural worldview of the native speaker and the native speaker of the target language. High degree of cultural marking of the considered examples quite often interferes with equivalent transfer of the content in a situation of contact of two cultures. However, even when such an equivalent does exist and is fixed in dictionaries, the translator cannot always be sure that the equivalent is included in the receptive dictionary of the final recipient.

In order to eliminate intercultural / interlingual lacunae in the field of economic intercultural communication, the most acceptable methods include descriptive translation (filling) in the form of translation-definition, translation-interpretation or translation with linguistic commentary, as well as the use of the corresponding equivalent in the target language (compensation). Filling (both linguistic and cultural) can be of different depths. It largely depends on the type of lacuna being eliminated, on the type of text in which the lacuna exists, as well as on the characteristics of the recipient to whom the text is addressed.

When working with lacunae, students can use various sources to obtain the missing information. Invaluable help is provided by electronic resources, allowing a wide search of information, both linguistic and cultural.

CONCLUSIONS

The processes of economics, information, and sociocultural globalization promote the unification of people of different ethnic groups in joint activities on the development of production (Bainiyazova, Yarmakeev, Akhmadullina, Valiakhmetova and Bekish, 2017).

In this regard, the role of translation as an element of the formation of linguo-cultural and sociocultural competences of students increases. Translation itself puts a student in a situation where he/she will have to act as an agent of

intercultural communication. Then, on his/her own experience, he/she can consciously perceive a clash of cultures when it is necessary to express meanings born in one culture by means of another language, i.e. another culture (Ayupova, 2016).

The main aim here is not only to prepare professional translators, but also to help students understand cultural differences and acquire skills of successful intercultural communication. A large part of the practical use of the language is associated with the command of linguistic realities that are directly related to the culture of the country that could include proper names, which have already become common (Marshall-Plan), geographical concepts that have a certain meaning for the representatives of this culture (Ruhrgebiet, Hamburg), significant events (Null-Stunde), some specific concepts (Indoctrination), abbreviations (BIP), and, of course, idioms and phraseological combinations (ArbeitsaufAbruf).

Translation, as a field of study, gives students the opportunity to understand that words and structures of one language cannot be mechanically replaced by similar elements of another. The translation process involves the analysis of the meanings of the source text and its conscious interpretation to create a new text, which will be clear to the representative of the recipient's culture. In the process of language teaching, it is necessary to use every opportunity to compare the linguo-cultural concepts and realities of Russia and the German-speaking countries, drawing the attention of students to the differences in the German language. Metacognitive approach proved to be effective due to self-controlling and self-reflecting (Ageeva, Abdullina, and Latypov, 2016).

While performing any translation tasks, students receive a large amount of linguo-cultural information as well as develop significant skills for intercultural communication, such as the ability to see intercultural differences. This ability also helps them to realize the necessity to develop a tolerant attitude to other's reflection and perception of the world, and to respect different viewpoints. Translation tasks also push students to develop the ability to express correctly and accurately their thoughts in their native language.

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REFERENCES

Ageeva, A., Abdullina, L., Latypov, N. (2016). **On-line / internet comments as the reflection of national mentality (case Analyze of the French and Russian languages)**. The Turkish Online Journal of Design, Art and Communication - TOJDAC July 2016 Special Edition. pp. 1016-1021.

Ayupova, R. (2016). **Teaching Oral Consecutive Interpretation**. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and Literature*, 5(7), pp. 163-167.

Bainiyazova, E., Yarmakeev, I., Akhmadullina, R., Valiakhmetova N., Bekish, E. (2017). **Formation of Ethnic Identity of School children By Means of Museum Pedagogics**. *Helix Vol. 8(1)*, pp.2460- 2464.

Sorokin, YU.A., Markovina. I.YU. (1988). **Culture and its own psychological psychology**, *Ethno-Psycholinguistics*. pp. 5–18.